

A SELF-INDICATING MODE I INTERLAMINAR TOUGHNESS TEST

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SUMMARY

This paper reports on the development of a Mode I interlaminar test which has been designed to indicate the crack position on the load-displacement curve so avoiding the requirement to monitor the crack length during the test. Results of the self-indicating test show good agreement with the conventional Mode I test method.

Keywords: Mode I, delamination, toughness

INTRODUCTION

The double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen, shown in Figure 1, has become the established specimen for the measurement of delamination toughness of composites in Mode I [1,2].

Figure 1: Conventional DCB specimen

The usual test procedure is to record force (P), displacement (δ) and crack length (a) as the delamination advances. A data reduction technique based on beam theory or compliance calibration is then applied to calculate the Mode I critical energy release rate, G_{Ic} . A disadvantage of the DCB specimen is that the crack length measurement is usually obtained by visual observation of one edge and as a consequence the results can vary according to the skills of the person conducting the test. Even if the test operator is

experienced the development a skewed crack front due to material variability or, in the case of woven composite specimens, the presence of multiple cracks due to disbonding of transverse yarns can lead to very uncertain measurement of crack lengths. It is possible to determine G_{Ic} without using the measured crack length but then the formula for G_{Ic} relies on an analytical expression for the specimen stiffness which itself may not be an accurate representation of the actual specimen behaviour. Another solution to the crack length problem is to avoid visual observation by using crack length gauges or other sensors attached to the specimen [3] but these can add expense and complexity to the test set up.

This paper explores a simple modification to the conventional DCB test specimen to make visual observation of the crack length unnecessary.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE APPROACH

The basis of the approach is to modify the specimen so that the crack length can be inferred from the load-displacement curve recorded in a test and to use the area method to determine G_{Ic} . The specimen is modified by altering the ‘starter’ delamination film. In the conventional test specimen this film is incorporated at the mid-plane of the laminate to provide the initial, or ‘starter’, delamination (Fig. 1). Various modified forms of the delamination film have been considered and some are shown in Figure 2. The initial growth in a specimen using pattern (a) is stable but as the crack front approaches the right hand edge of the first laminated rectangular zone the crack growth becomes unstable and the crack will arrest after partial growth into the next laminated zone. The unstable growth means that data reduction using the area method is not valid.

Figure 2: Modified delamination patterns

An alternative pattern of delamination film, which will ensure stable crack growth, is shown in Figure 2b. Here the crack front initially advances through a laminated zone of constant width in a stable manner and, assuming that G_{Ic} remains constant, the load will be steadily reducing. When a step increase in laminated zone width is encountered the crack growth will arrest and an increase in load will be recorded on the load-

displacement plot until crack growth restarts in the wider laminated zone. The energy consumed as the crack grows from the start to the end of one of the constant width laminated zones can be determined and hence, using the area of the zone, G_{Ic} can be calculated. It is important that the steps in the laminated width are sufficiently large to cause a suitably distinct change in the load-displacement curve and with this in mind the possible number of steps in laminated zone width will be limited by the width of the specimen for the pattern of Figure 2b. This limitation can be overcome by using a pattern of the type shown in Figure 2c in which, between the step changes, the width of the laminated zone steadily reduces with crack length – though clearly there is the potential for unstable growth in the tapered width zones. This pattern is the basis of the self-indicating Mode I toughness specimen which is explored in this paper.

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF THE SELF-INDICATING SPECIMEN

This section analyses the geometry influence on the crack growth stability for the pattern of Figure 2c and describes the pattern design used in the test programme.

Stability analysis

Figure 3 defines the geometry of the initial part of the self-indicating starter delamination pattern with the crack front having advanced a distance $(a-a_1^*)$ into the first laminated zone where a is the distance to the crack front and a_1^* is the distance to the start of the first laminated zone, both measured from the load line.

Figure 3: Geometry of the self-indicating pattern

The energy release rate at the crack front is given by

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2w} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

in which P is the applied load, w is the width of the delamination crack front and C is the compliance (i.e. δ/P). To cause crack growth P must be sufficiently large to ensure

$$G_I = G_{Ic} \quad (2)$$

For crack growth to be stable the following condition must be satisfied

$$\frac{dG_I}{da} < \frac{dG_{Ic}}{da} \quad (3)$$

and if G_{Ic} is assumed to be constant then this condition becomes

$$\frac{dG_I}{da} < 0 \quad (4)$$

Treating each arm of the specimen as a cantilever which is built-in across the full width of the specimen at the crack front, the arm compliance from simple beam theory is

$$C = \frac{2a^3}{3EI} \quad (5)$$

where E is the longitudinal Young's modulus of the arm material and I is the 2nd moment of area of the arm cross section. Replacing P in equation 1 as δC and substituting for C using equation 5 then the condition for stable crack growth (equation 4) can be shown to be satisfied for a displacement-controlled test providing the crack length meets the following condition:

$$a < \frac{4}{5}(l_1 + a_1^*) \quad (6)$$

in which l_1 is 'length' of the triangle of which that laminated zone forms part. Equation 6 defines the criterion for stability for crack growth in the initial laminated zone of the pattern of Figure 3.

Equation 6 can be also applied to crack growth in the subsequent laminated zones; for the i^{th} laminated zone a_1^* and l_1 are replaced by the values of a_i^* and of l_i .

Specimen design

To simplify the design of the self-indicating specimen, the values of l_i and a'_i (the length of the i^{th} laminated zone) are set to constant values, l and a' respectively, and by choosing the starting width of each laminated zone to be equal to that of the first zone (i.e. B_1) then the areas of the laminated zones are all equal. To ensure stable growth up to the end of the i^{th} laminated zone there must be sufficient laminated material beyond the end of this zone to ensure that the built-in assumption is still reasonable and the following condition on the length of each laminated zone must be satisfied.

$$a' < \frac{4l - a_1^*}{i + 4} \quad (7)$$

An additional condition, which is important in the specimen design, concerns the step increase in laminated width at the junctions between consecutive laminated zones. The load, P_{init} , required to initiate crack growth in the next laminated zone is related to the

load, P_{arr} , at crack arrest at the end of the previous laminated zone, according to simple beam theory, by the following equation.

$$\frac{P_{init}}{P_{arr}} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\text{width at start of laminated zone}}{\text{width at end of laminated zone}} \right]} \quad (8)$$

Equation 8 can be used to ensure that there is a sufficiently distinct change in the load-displacement curve during the crack-arrest phase between consecutive laminated zones. Table 1 gives the geometry of the self-indicating specimen designed using equations 7 and 8 for the experimental evaluation.

Table 1: Dimensions of the self-indicating specimen

No. of laminated zones	a^* (mm)	a' (mm)	l (mm)	B (mm)	B_l (mm)
5	50	28	80	30	20

EVALUATION OF THE SELF-INDICATING APPROACH

Manufacturing details

Three types of specimen were prepared (see Fig. 4). These were self-indicating specimens, conventional DCB specimens (to provide a G_{Ic} value for comparison with that measured with the self indicating specimens) and specimens containing a single triangular shaped laminated zone (to assess the accuracy of the stability criterion of equation 6).

Figure 4: Geometry of the test specimens (dimensions in mm)

Materials

All specimens were manufactured from panels of unidirectional carbon epoxy laminate laid up using a Hexcel prepreg (914C-T300-6K). To produce the required starter

delamination pattern a 12.5 μm Teflon film was incorporated at the mid-plane of the laminate. All laminates were 330 mm (fibre direction) x 300 mm and consisted of 24 plies giving a nominal cured thickness of 3 mm.

Preparation and insertion of delamination pattern

To reduce the effect of any variation in G_{Ic} between laminates or within a laminate, the three different types of specimens were interspersed as uniformly as was practical across the prepared laminates. Therefore a fairly complex delamination starter pattern of the type shown in Figure 5 had to be cut and positioned within the prepreg assembly. The pattern included small cut-outs along the outer edges which are used to correctly cut the specimens from the cured panel.

Figure 5: Example of starter delamination pattern

To prepare the film, a full-scale drawing of the required delamination pattern was printed and taped to cardboard on a flat working surface. A transparent sheet of Melinex film (0.05mm thick) was taped over the drawing and the Teflon delamination film was placed on top of the Melinex. The Teflon layer adhered naturally to the Melinex due to static electricity and did not need to be taped to hold it in position. A scalpel and ruler were then used to cut the required pattern along the lines of the pattern drawing which was visible through the film layers. Care was taken not to cut completely through the Melinex layer as much as possible.

Once the pattern had been completely cut, all the loose pieces of Teflon film were removed (i.e. in the positions that would form the laminated zones). The backing film was removed from one face of a 12-ply prepreg assembly and the exposed face was positioned carefully onto the Teflon film. The tape securing Melinex was then cut and the Melinex, Teflon and prepreg assembly was then inverted and the Melinex carefully peeled away from the Teflon layer which was left adhered to the surface of the prepreg.

Another 12-ply prepreg assembly was then positioned on top of the film to complete the layup.

Curing and preparation of specimens

The laminates were cured in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations but omitting the post-cure procedure. One surface of each panel was marked out with strips of approximately 5 mm width along the edges of the panel and perpendicular to these strips two to three short lines, to be used as alignment guides, were marked along each edge across the strip width into the interior of the panel. These strips were then cut from the edge of the panel and each strip was separated at its mid-plane to locate the cut-outs (see Fig. 5). The position of the cut-outs were measured relative to the alignment lines and were marked on the edge of the remainder of the panel. From the original cutting pattern drawing the positions of all the specimens could then be marked out and the specimens machined from the panel.

Specimen preparation was completed by adhesively bonding aluminum loading blocks at the loading end of each specimen and marking a scale along one edge of each conventional DCB specimen for monitoring the crack growth.

Test Procedure

The specimens were tested in a 100 kN Instron test frame fitted with a 500 N load cell. The tests were conducted at a crosshead displacement speed of 2 mm/minute and during each test load and crosshead displacement data were recorded by computer. For the conventional DCB test a CCD camera was used to enable a greatly magnified image of the crack tip zone on one edge of the specimen to be observed on a monitor. As the crack reached each crack length increment an event marker signal was recorded with the associated load and displacement data. In the case of the conventional DCB specimen the crack was grown by 50mm before the test was halted and the specimen unloaded. The tests of the self-indicating specimens were stopped after the crack growth had passed through the final specially shaped laminated zone. For the triangle delamination pattern specimens each specimen was tested until the crack growth became unstable and the fracture surface was then examined by eye to determine the location of the transition from stable to unstable growth.

Results

Load-displacement data

The conventional DCB specimens showed the characteristic steady reduction in load as the crack advanced. For the self-indicating specimens, the typical load-displacement curve is shown in Figure 6. This plot clearly shows the increase in load which occurs in when the crack front reaches a step-change in the laminated zone width. The plot also shows a steady reduction in load as the crack advances through each laminated zone indicating that the crack growth was stable as intended. The triangle delamination specimens all showed an initial steady reduction in applied load as the crack grew and a sharp drop in load when the crack growth became unstable.

The crack length, a_{crit} , at onset of the unstable growth is presented in Table 2 together with the predicted value according to equation 6. The actual crack length at the onset of

unstable growth exceeded the theoretical prediction by approximately 10mm for all the specimens.

Figure 6: Typical load-displacement plot for the self-indicating specimens

Table 2: Crack length at onset of unstable growth in ‘Triangle’ specimens

Specimen type (see Fig. 4)	a_{crit} (mm)		
	Experiment	Experiment average	Theory (eq. 6)
A	115	114.5	104
	116		
	113		
	114		
B	113	115	104
	114		
	118		

Data Reduction

The modified beam theory data reduction scheme [1,2] was used to determine G_{Ic} from the conventional DCB test data. As indicated earlier, the area method was used for the self-indicating specimens. The energy consumed, U_i , as the crack advanced from the start of the i^{th} laminated zone to the next (see Fig. 7) was determined from the load-displacement data as

$$U_i = \frac{P_i \delta_i}{2} + \int_{\delta_i}^{\delta_{i+1}} P d\delta - \frac{P_{i+1} \delta_{i+1}}{2} \quad (9)$$

in which P_i and δ_i are the load and displacement at the maximum of the load-displacement curve associated with the start of the i^{th} laminated zone. The value of G_{Ic} was then calculated by dividing U_i by the area, $A_{lam,i}$, of the i^{th} laminated zone. In the

self-indicating specimens used here the area of the laminated zones was constant, A_{lam} , and so the value of G_{Ic} was given by

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{U_i}{A_{lam}} \quad (10)$$

Figure 7: Calculation of energy consumed for self-indicating specimen

A MATLAB program was written to locate the maximum associated with the start of each laminated zone, to numerically evaluate the integral of equation 9 and, finally, to calculate G_{Ic} according to equation 10.

G_{Ic} results

The mode I interlaminar toughness measured with the conventional DCB specimen displayed a slight rising R-curve as shown in Figure 8. The average toughness measured in five specimens rose from approximately 0.11 kJ/m^2 at initiation to approximately 0.13 kJ/m^2 at the end of the 50mm of crack growth. The scatter of data at a particular crack length was generally contained within a band of $\pm 0.005 \text{ kJ/m}^2$.

The data from the self-indicating tests are shown in Figure 8 where for each laminated zone the average value of G_{Ic} of all five specimens tested is plotted as a line over the crack length range associated with that laminated zone. The range of toughnesses for a given laminated zone was typically $\pm 0.015 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ which is rather larger than that observed in the DCB specimens for a given crack length.

The toughness measured in the first laminated zone is higher than from the conventional DCB test but this may be because the crack front profile varies during the test. The crack front shape at the first peak in the load-displacement trace (associated with initiation of growth) is unlikely to be identical to the shape at the next peak (associated with the junction of adjacent laminated zones) and so the area swept through by the crack front between the first two peaks may not be equal to A_{lam} . It can be observed that the G_{Ic} value measured in the second laminated zone is only slightly higher than the DCB values and that the rising G_{Ic} trend in the conventional DCB specimens is also seen in the data from the self-indicating specimens.

Figure 8: G_{Ic} data from conventional DCB and self-indicating specimens

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that by suitably modifying the delamination film pattern in a conventional DCB specimen, the area swept out by the crack front can be inferred from distinct features on the experimental load-displacement trace. It is therefore possible to determine G_{Ic} using an area-based data reduction method without direct observation of the crack length. Such an approach may be useful for woven composite laminates for which crack length observation is difficult. The data reduction procedure can be completely automated and may therefore be suitable for quality control testing.

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References

1. ASTM D5528-01(2007)e2. Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites
2. ISO 15024:2001. Fibre-reinforced plastic composites -- Determination of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , for unidirectionally reinforced materials
3. S. Yarlagadda, A. Abu Obaid, M. K. Yoon, N. Hager, R. Domszy "An Automated Technique for Measuring Crack Propagation during Mode I DCB Testing", Society of Experimental Mechanics, X International Congress, Hilton Costa Mesa, 2004 June 7-10